

Narcotic Analgesics and Psychotropic Agents in Emergency Medicine: A Retrospective Clinical and Analytical Review of the Prehospital Stage and Modern Trends

Viktor Yuriev

National Technical University 'Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute'

Kharkiv, Ukraine

viktor.yuriev60@gmail.com

Abstract

The article presents a retrospective clinical and analytical review of the use of narcotic analgesics and psychotropic agents in acute and critical conditions during the prehospital stage of emergency medical care. The study is based on the analysis of medical documentation from the emergency medical service of the city of Kharkiv for the year 2003. The pharmacological properties, mechanisms of action, clinical indications, routes of administration, and adverse effects of narcotic analgesics and psychotropic agents used in urgent medical practice are discussed. An analysis of the structure of clinical conditions, the frequency of administration of individual medications, and the principles governing their prehospital use was performed.

Special attention is paid to the evolution of contemporary approaches to prehospital analgesia and sedation, including multimodal analgesia, opioid-sparing strategies, procedural sedation protocols, the use of ketamine, capnography, and modern safe sedation protocols. The presented data make it possible to trace the continuity of the fundamental principles of emergency medicine and their transformation in the context of current international guidelines.

Keywords: emergency medical care, prehospital stage, narcotic analgesics, morphine, fentanyl, ketamine, procedural sedation, capnography, opioid-sparing analgesia, psychotropic agents, neuroleptanalgesia.

Introduction

Narcotic analgesics and psychotropic agents have traditionally occupied an important place in emergency medical practice, particularly in the management of patients with acute and life-threatening conditions [1–4]. Severe pain syndromes, pronounced psychomotor agitation, convulsive states, acute respiratory failure, and cardiovascular insufficiency require rapid and clinically justified pharmacological intervention already at the prehospital stage.

A characteristic feature of emergency medical service teams is the necessity to make decisions under conditions of limited time, incomplete diagnostic information, and an increased risk of complications. Under such circumstances, narcotic analgesics and psychotropic agents not only allow the control of the leading clinical syndrome but also help stabilize the patient's condition, ensure safe transportation, and prepare the patient for further specialized treatment.

Despite the considerable evolution of international clinical guidelines and the expansion of the pharmacological arsenal in emergency medicine, the fundamental principles of urgent pharmacotherapy — individualized treatment, dose titration, prioritization of safety, and continuous clinical assessment of the patient's condition — remain highly relevant [1,2,12].

The analysis of historical clinical experience in prehospital medicine is of both practical and methodological interest, as it allows tracing the evolution of approaches to analgesia, sedation, and intensive care in urgent medical practice.

Objective

The aim of the present study was to conduct a retrospective clinical and analytical review of the use of narcotic analgesics and psychotropic agents in acute conditions at the prehospital stage of emergency medical care, with an assessment of clinical effectiveness, safety, and comparison with modern trends in emergency medicine.

Materials and Methods

A retrospective analysis of medical documentation from the emergency medical service of the city of Kharkiv for the year 2003 was performed.

The study included cases involving the administration of narcotic analgesics and psychotropic agents to patients with acute conditions during the prehospital stage.

The following parameters were analyzed:

- clinical indications for drug administration;
- structure of urgent conditions;
- frequency of administration of individual medications;
- routes of administration;
- immediate clinical effect;
- recorded adverse reactions and complications.

The study methods included descriptive statistical analysis and clinical interpretation of the obtained data, taking into account the pharmacological properties of the medications and the specific features of urgent conditions. Statistical processing was descriptive in nature and included analysis of absolute and relative indicators.

Results and Discussion

Clinical Scenarios for Drug Administration at the Prehospital Stage

In emergency medical care, a syndrome-oriented approach to the administration of narcotic analgesics and psychotropic agents is fundamentally important. The choice of medication is determined not so much by the nosological form of the disease as by the leading clinical syndrome threatening the patient's condition at the specific moment of care delivery.

The most significant clinical scenarios included:

- severe pain syndrome in acute coronary syndrome and myocardial infarction;
- dyspnea and pain component in pulmonary edema;
- traumatic and cardiogenic shock;
- convulsive syndrome of various etiologies;
- psychomotor agitation accompanied by pronounced autonomic reactions.

It was precisely within these conditions that the principal pharmacological effects of the investigated medications were realized.

Structure of the Use of Narcotic Analgesics and Psychotropic Agents

Analysis of the medical documentation demonstrated that the most frequent indications for the administration of narcotic analgesics and psychotropic agents were acute coronary syndrome, traumatic injuries, convulsive syndrome, pulmonary edema, and psychomotor agitation.

Table 1. Use of Narcotic Analgesics and Psychotropic Agents at EMS Substation No. 10 in Kharkiv in 2003

Disease / Condition	Morphine	Omnopon	Fentanyl	Sibazone	Sodium Oxybutyrate	Total
Unstable angina	7	19	29	–	–	55
Acute myocardial infarction	18	15	31	–	–	64
Pulmonary edema	67	–	1	–	–	68
Trauma	–	10	2	–	1	13
Oncological diseases	2	5	2	–	2	11
Convulsive syndrome	–	–	–	61	73	134
Status epilepticus	–	–	–	15	11	26
Bronchial asthma	–	–	–	–	3	3
Other diseases	–	2	1	–	80	83
Total	94	51	66	76	170	457

In 2003, emergency medical teams of EMS Substation No. 10 in Kharkiv responded to 21,373 calls, including 2,423 outpatient visits.

A diagnosis of ischemic heart disease and unstable angina was established in 380 cases. Narcotic analgesics were administered to 55 patients. In all cases, the administration of narcotic analgesics resulted in successful relief of anginal pain and stabilization of the patients' condition before transportation to the hospital.

Morphine was the most frequently used narcotic analgesic and was primarily administered in acute coronary syndrome, myocardial infarction, traumatic shock, and pulmonary edema.

Fentanyl was used in urgent situations requiring rapid onset of analgesic effect, including as part of neuroleptanalgesia in combination with droperidol [7,8].

Among psychotropic agents, sibazone was of greatest importance and was mainly used for the management of convulsive syndrome and psychomotor agitation [9–11].

Main Clinical Indications

Table 2. Main Clinical Conditions and Characteristics of Drug Administration

Clinical condition	Number of cases	Characteristics of therapy
Unstable angina	380	Narcotic analgesics administered to 55 patients
Acute myocardial infarction	79	Narcotic analgesics administered 64 times
Pulmonary edema	90	Morphine used 67 times
Traumatic shock	12	Narcotic analgesics administered in all cases
Convulsive syndrome	61	Main drug — sibazone
Status epilepticus	15	Sibazone and sodium oxybutyrate

Acute myocardial infarction was diagnosed in 79 cases. Narcotic analgesics were administered 64 times for the relief of coronary pain syndrome. Preference was given to fentanyl because of its rapid onset of action following intravenous administration.

The combination of fentanyl (0.1 mg) and droperidol (5 mg) in the form of neuroleptanalgesia was administered to 23 patients with acute myocardial infarction. A complete analgesic effect was observed in approximately 60% of patients. In a number of cases, sequential administration of different narcotic analgesics was required to achieve complete relief of the coronary pain syndrome.

Acute myocardial infarction was complicated by the development of pulmonary edema in 9 cases. Morphine was administered to all patients as part of комплексной therapy.

Acute pulmonary edema was diagnosed in 90 patients. Morphine was administered 67 times, contributing to the reduction of dyspnea, decreased pressure in the pulmonary circulation, and improvement of hemodynamic parameters.

Skeletal trauma was complicated by traumatic shock in 12 patients. In all cases, emergency medical service teams administered narcotic analgesics: omnopon in 10 cases and fentanyl in 2 cases.

Narcotic Analgesics

The principal representative of the group of narcotic analgesics in emergency medical practice was morphine, the main alkaloid of opium with a pronounced analgesic effect [5,6]. In therapeutic doses, morphine effectively relieves pain syndrome without impairing consciousness or motor activity.

The analgesic effect of morphine is associated with its influence on thalamic structures and the reduction of nociceptive impulse transmission to the cerebral cortex [5,6]. Its effects on the respiratory center and neuroendocrine stress response are also of considerable importance.

At the prehospital stage, morphine was used in:

- myocardial infarction;
- acute coronary syndrome;
- dissecting aortic aneurysm;
- thromboembolic conditions;
- spontaneous pneumothorax;
- traumatic shock;
- acute left ventricular failure.

Despite its high efficacy, the use of morphine was limited by the risk of respiratory depression, arterial hypotension, bradycardia, nausea, and vomiting.

Omnopon was used primarily in pain syndromes accompanied by a spastic component.

Fentanyl, as a synthetic narcotic analgesic, was characterized by rapid onset and short duration of action, making it particularly convenient in urgent clinical situations [7,8].

Psychotropic Agents

Among psychotropic agents, benzodiazepines and neuroleptics were of greatest importance.

Sibazone was widely used for the management of convulsive syndrome of various etiologies, including:

- epileptic seizures;
- status epilepticus;
- febrile seizures in children;
- convulsive conditions associated with acute cerebrovascular disorders [9–11].

The medication was administered predominantly intravenously with consideration of the patient's clinical condition.

In cases of refractory convulsive syndrome, sodium oxybutyrate possessing sedative and central muscle-relaxant properties was used.

Aminazine and droperidol were administered for the management of psychomotor agitation and sympathoadrenal hypertensive crises. Droperidol was also used as a component of neuroleptanalgesia.

Psychotropic Agents and Specific Features of Their Administration

The most frequently used psychotropic medications included:

- sibazone 0.5% — 2.0 mL;
- sodium oxybutyrate 20% — 10.0 mL;
- droperidol 0.25% — 2.0 mL;
- aminazine 2.5% — 2.0 mL.

Sibazone was primarily used for the treatment of convulsive syndrome of various etiologies. In 2003, the medication was used in 61 cases of convulsive syndrome, including epileptic seizures, febrile seizures in children, and acute cerebrovascular disorders accompanied by seizures.

Status epilepticus was registered in 15 patients. In cases of status epilepticus, adults received intravenous sibazone at a dose of 10 mg diluted in glucose solution. If necessary, the administration was repeated every 10–15 minutes until a total dose of 30 mg was reached.

In 50% of status epilepticus cases, intravenous sodium oxybutyrate was required in addition to sibazone. In total, sodium oxybutyrate was administered 170 times to 160 patients.

Aminazine was used for the management of psychomotor agitation, anxiety, pronounced autonomic reactions, and psychotic states. Overall, the medication was used in 597 cases.

Droperidol was administered both as part of neuroleptanalgesia and for the treatment of sympathoadrenal hypertensive crises. In total, the medication was administered to 368 patients in 2003.

Adverse Effects and Complications

The principal complications associated with the use of narcotic analgesics included the risk of respiratory depression, arterial hypotension, bradycardia, nausea, and vomiting. The highest risk of complications was observed during intravenous administration of the medications.

For this reason, preference was given to titrated intravenous administration of narcotic analgesics under continuous monitoring of the patient's condition and hemodynamic parameters.

Modern Trends in Prehospital Analgesia and Sedation

In recent years, approaches to analgesia, sedation, and patient safety at the prehospital stage have evolved considerably under the influence of international clinical guidelines and the development of the prehospital critical care concept [12–18]. Alongside the traditional use of narcotic analgesics and classical psychotropic medications, increasing importance has been attributed to multimodal analgesia, opioid-sparing strategies, procedural sedation protocols, and advanced monitoring methods.

One of the most significant developments has been the introduction of ketamine into emergency medical practice. Ketamine is regarded as an effective medication for analgesia and dissociative sedation in polytrauma, burns, severe pain syndromes, and painful procedures [14–16]. A substantial advantage of ketamine is its relative hemodynamic stability and minimal respiratory depression compared with opioids and benzodiazepines.

Current guidelines consider ketamine one of the components of opioid-sparing analgesia, allowing reduction in the requirement for high doses of narcotic analgesics [14,15].

Additional development has occurred in the use of intranasal fentanyl, particularly in pediatric patients and trauma cases when intravenous access is difficult [15,16].

Modern approaches to procedural sedation involve the use of standardized algorithms for patient assessment, risk stratification, and continuous monitoring during sedation [14,16].

Prehospital RSI (rapid sequence intubation) has become particularly important in prehospital critical care practice and is used in severe respiratory failure, polytrauma, and critically decreased levels of consciousness [17].

Capnography has become an integral component of modern safe sedation. Monitoring the concentration of carbon dioxide in exhaled air allows timely detection of hypoventilation and early signs of respiratory depression [16,18].

SAFE sedation protocols are becoming increasingly widespread in international practice. These protocols are based on comprehensive patient assessment, standardization of sedation procedures, preparedness for airway management, and continuous patient monitoring [14,16].

Historical and Clinical Interpretation of the Data

The presented materials reflect the specific characteristics of prehospital emergency medical practice in the early 2000s, when the pharmacological arsenal of emergency medical service teams differed substantially from contemporary international protocols.

The widespread use of morphine, droperidol, omnopon, and neuroleptanalgesia corresponded to the prevailing concepts of pain syndrome and psychomotor agitation management in urgent medical practice at that time.

At the same time, the analysis demonstrates that several fundamental principles remain relevant in modern emergency medicine:

- syndrome-oriented approach;
- dose titration;
- priority of rapid pain relief;
- necessity for respiratory and hemodynamic monitoring;
- individualized therapy.

Modern international guidelines have significantly expanded the possibilities of prehospital analgesia and sedation through the implementation of ketamine, procedural sedation protocols, capnography, and opioid-sparing strategies; however, the basic clinical principles of urgent pharmacotherapy remain continuous.

Conclusions

Narcotic analgesics and psychotropic agents were important and highly effective components of emergency medical care in acute conditions at the prehospital stage.

The most frequent indications for the administration of these medications were acute coronary syndrome, traumatic shock, convulsive syndrome, pulmonary edema, and psychomotor agitation. Rational drug selection, dose titration, and continuous monitoring of vital functions increased therapeutic effectiveness and reduced the risk of complications.

Retrospective analysis of emergency medical practice in the early 2000s demonstrates the continuity of the fundamental principles of urgent pharmacotherapy and their correspondence with modern approaches to safe analgesia and sedation.

Contemporary trends in the development of prehospital medicine are associated with the implementation of multimodal analgesia, ketamine, procedural sedation protocols, capnography, and opioid-sparing strategies.

Training of emergency physicians should include in-depth study of pharmacology, principles of safe sedation, and modern guideline-based approaches to prehospital analgesia.

References

1. Tintinalli JE, Ma OJ, Yealy DM, et al. *Tintinalli's Emergency Medicine: A Comprehensive Study Guide*. 9th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill; 2020.
2. Walls RM, Hockberger RS, Gausche-Hill M. *Rosen's Emergency Medicine: Concepts and Clinical Practice*. 9th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2018.
3. American College of Emergency Physicians. Clinical policy: Critical issues in the evaluation and management of adult patients presenting to the emergency department with acute pain. *Ann Emerg Med*. 2017;69(5):e1–e31.
4. World Health Organization. *WHO Guidelines on the Pharmacological Treatment of Persisting Pain*. Geneva: WHO; 2019.
5. Goodman LS, Gilman A. *The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics*. 13th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill; 2018.
6. Katzung BG, Trevor AJ. *Basic & Clinical Pharmacology*. 15th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill; 2021.
7. Miller RD, Cohen NH. *Miller's Anesthesia*. 9th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2020.
8. Stoelting RK, Hillier SC. *Pharmacology and Physiology in Anesthetic Practice*. 5th ed. Philadelphia: Wolters Kluwer; 2015.
9. Shorvon S. *The Treatment of Epilepsy*. 4th ed. Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell; 2016.
10. Brophy GM, Bell R, Claassen J, et al. Guidelines for the evaluation and management of status epilepticus. *Neurocrit Care*. 2012;17(1):3–23.
11. Glauser T, Shinnar S, Gloss D, et al. Evidence-based guideline: Treatment of convulsive status epilepticus in children and adults. *Epilepsy Curr*. 2016;16(1):48–61.
12. Nolan JP, Soar J, Cariou A, et al. European Resuscitation Council Guidelines for Resuscitation 2021. *Resuscitation*. 2021;161:1–60.
13. Prehospital Trauma Life Support Committee. *PHTLS: Prehospital Trauma Life Support*. 9th ed. Burlington: Jones & Bartlett Learning; 2019.
14. Godwin SA, Burton JH, Gerardo CJ, et al. Clinical policy: Procedural sedation and analgesia in the emergency department. *Ann Emerg Med*. 2014;63(2):247–58.
15. Motov S, Mai M, Pushkar I, et al. A prospective randomized study of intravenous subdissociative-dose ketamine versus morphine for analgesia in the emergency department. *Ann Emerg Med*. 2015;66(3):222–9.
16. Green SM, Roback MG, Kennedy RM, Krauss B. Clinical practice guideline for emergency department ketamine dissociative sedation. *Ann Emerg Med*. 2011;57(5):449–61.
17. Walls RM, Murphy MF. *Manual of Emergency Airway Management*. 5th ed. Philadelphia: Wolters Kluwer; 2018.
18. Deitch K, Miner J, Chudnofsky CR, et al. Does end tidal CO₂ monitoring during emergency department procedural sedation and analgesia with propofol decrease the incidence of hypoxic events? A randomized controlled trial. *Ann Emerg Med*. 2010;55(3):258–64.